

Hollow-Core Fiber Specifications for Competitive Deployment in Regio/Long-Haul Optical Networks

Bruno Correia¹, João Pedro^{1,2}, Nelson Costa¹

⁽¹⁾ *Infinera Unipessoal Lda, Rua da Garagem 1, 2790-078 Carnaxide, Portugal*

⁽²⁾ *Instituto de Telecomunicações, Instituto Superior Técnico, 1049-001 Lisboa, Portugal*

bcorreia@infinera.com

Abstract: Steady progress in hollow-core fiber (HCF) technology raises the prospect of wide-scale deployments. This paper characterizes the combination of fiber and optical amplifier specifications for HCF to achieve performance parity with commercial SSMF and PSCF. © 2025 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Hollow-core fibers (HCF) have seen a significant evolution in recent years, presenting several advantages when compared with traditional fused silica optical ones. They have a much lower theoretical loss and wide spectral low-loss region as they are not limited by the Rayleigh scattering [1], with several low-loss records established recently [2, 3]. A record loss of 0.11 dB/km was obtained with the Double Nested Antiresonant Nodeless Fiber (DNANF) [3], a specific HCF design referred to in this work as NANF. These fibers show also low non-linearity and negligible stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) effect [4, 5]. Consequently, HCF transmission may achieve higher channel capacity than traditional optical fibers, specially when using high power per channel [6]. Nowadays, optical amplifiers used in core network deployments usually have a maximum output power smaller than 27 dBm, although there are commercially available devices with higher output power [7]. Additionally, the transmission of light through near-vacuum medium, as in the case of HCF, increases in 50% the speed of transmission compared with traditional optical fibers, a property that can have a paramount impact in latency-constrained scenarios [8]. Nevertheless, transmission in these fibers is impacted by the Inter-Modal-Interference (IMI), the fundamental mode loss induced by high order modes during fiber transmission. Early studies have shown that the impact of IMI can be neglected when it is smaller than -60.0 dB/km [6]. However, several works have shown that the HCF IMI was in the -40.0 to -55 dB/km range [2, 3, 5]. This result leads to the conclusion that IMI cannot be neglected in general. When compared to traditional fiber deployments, HCF deployment also suffers from increased connection losses, such as splice losses and losses at the interconnection with traditional fibers (required to leverage existing amplifiers and ROADM nodes). These losses have been decreasing, currently achieving around 0.18 dB per splice [9, 10]. Importantly, since the wider deployment of HCF will require a manufacturing process at scale, there is still no reliable characterization of a commercial HCF loss coefficient and IMI value. Moreover, sloppy fiber roll-out, aging and splices as a result of cuts also mean that realistic splice losses are also unknown. Bearing these uncertainties in mind, this work intends to characterize the range of key parameters which make an HCF based deployment competitive when compared to a Standard Single-Mode Fiber (SSMF) or Pure-Silica-Core Fiber (PSCF) deployment, in regio/long-haul optical networks. To the best of our knowledge, the only work that addresses the viability of HCF in these networks is presented in [11], but which ignored the impact of both IMI and splice losses and did not model the range of potential variations in losses and amplifier output power.

2. Fiber Characterization and Performance Model

The quality of transmission (QoT) evaluation is done using the generalized signal-to-noise ratio (GSNR) metric, following the approach proposed in [6]. This metric accounts for the impact of the amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) and nonlinear interference (NLI) noise powers (P_{ASE} and P_{NLI}). For NANF transmission, a third noise source, the IMI power (P_{IMI}), is added. Hence, the GSNR can be computed as $GSNR = \frac{P_{ch}}{(P_{ASE} + P_{NLI} + P_{IMI})}$. It is worth noting that our simulations were performed by extending the open-source GNPpy framework [12], by adding the missing parameters. Fig. 1(a) shows the attenuation profile for SSMF (blue) and PSCF (orange), as well as the attenuation range tested for NANF (red), corresponding to a 0.1 dB variation around the SSMF loss.

We assume splices are made 2 km apart. For SSMF and PSCF, we consider a splice loss of 0.02 dB, whereas for NANF we evaluate a range between 0.06 and 0.5 dB. A NANF IMI parameter ranging between -60 and -45 dB/km is assumed. The amplifier maximum output power is set to be in the 27 to 36 dBm range. Fig. 1(b) plots the Raman gain coefficient for each fiber type. For NANF, we assume that the SRS effect is negligible [5]. Table. 1 shows the fiber characterization.

Fig. 1: (a) Fiber attenuation profile; (b) Raman gain coefficient; (c) Dependence of the GSNR on the power/ch in a 80 km long SSMF span; (d) Δ GSNR between SSMF and NANF (IMI=-55 dB/km, launch power=27 dBm).

We assume the transmission of 40 (36) channels in the SuperC (L)-band with each channel consisting in a 120 Gbaud signal transmitted in a 150 GHz grid. Consequently, a total bandwidth of about 12 THz is occupied (a band guard of 300 GHz is set). The amplifier noise-figure is assumed to be 5.5 and 6.0 dB for SuperC- and SuperL-band, respectively. The optimum launch power in each transmission band is found by a search grid. The optimization for an 80 km SSMF span is depicted in the heat-map of Fig. 1(c), leading to an optimum input power per channel of 5.8 dBm for Super C- and 3.6 dBm for Super L-band. In the case of using PSCF, optimum launch power per channel of 6.2 dBm and 4.6 dBm were found for the Super C and Super L-band, respectively.

In order to analyse the NANF performance in a real network scenario, the Deutsche Telekom (DT) network [13], with 132 routes in total, covering lengths up to 1040 km, is considered. The channel capacity is defined from a set of five formats based on 800G coherent pluggable multi-source agreement, with data rates ranging between 400 and 800 Gbps, for a required GSNR between 24 and 30 dB/0.1nm, respectively, already counting with 3 dB of margins. The transmitter optical signal-to-noise ratio (OSNR) is set to 37 dB/0.1nm and ROADMs losses to 20 dB.

Table 1: Fiber characterization.

Fiber parameters	SSMF	PSCF	NANF
Chromatic dispersion [ps/(nm.km)]	16.8	21.0	3.0
Chromatic dispersion slope [ps/((nm ²).km)]	0.058	0.061	0.0
Effective area [μm^2]	83	130	417
Nonlinear coefficient [1/(W.km)]	1.12E+00	6.24E-01	5.01E-04

3. Results and Conclusion

To ease the comparison between the NANF and SSMF/PSCF optical performance, we define the Δ GSNR = $\text{GSNR}_{\text{NANF}} - \text{GSNR}_{\text{SSMF/PSCF}}$. Fig. 1(d) depicts the heat-map of a 80 km span when SSMF is used as reference, the IMI of NANF is set equal to -55 dB/km and the maximum output power of booster is set to 27 dBm. The red region corresponds to the NANF parameter combinations for which it is preferable to use the SSMF whereas the green region is the opposite. The white region corresponds to the area where NANF and SSMF achieve similar optical performance (optical performance parity). The results show that a GSNR advantage of 11.5 dB may be attained when using the most optimistic combination of NANF parameters considered in this work.

Fig. 2(a) presents the curves of performance parity between SSMF and NANF for several IMI values and maximum launch power values of 27 dBm (circles) and 36 dBm (triangles). For both launch powers, we notice there is almost no variation when increasing the IMI power from -60 to -55 dB/km. However, higher IMI values, particularly IMI = -45 dB/km, impose stringent requirements in NANF fiber attenuation and splice loss. In this case, employing amplifiers with higher output power allows to offset the extra degradation (e.g., an extra attenuation of around 0.11 dB/km can be accommodated while preserving performance parity). In our simulations, increasing IMI noise significantly above -45 dB/km resulted in NANF always having worst performance than SSMF, even considering amplifiers with higher output power. Fig. 2(b) shows the curves of performance parity with PSCF. Similarly to the results with SSMF, there is a negligible impact of increasing IMI from -60 to -55 dB/km. However, when considering an IMI of -50 and -45 dB/km, NANF only becomes competitive with PSCF for significantly lower values of fiber attenuation and splice loss. For instance, when using amplifiers with 27 dBm of output power, a NANF with IMI of -50 dB/km and splice loss of 0.18 only attains parity with PSCF if it can feature a fiber attenuation of 0.17 dB/km. This threshold for performance parity can be substantially increased to around 0.28 dB/km if amplifiers with 36 dBm output power (and same noise figures) are available.

Fig. 2: Performance parity curves for NANF vs. (a) SSMF and (b) PSCF; (c) percentage of cases where NANF outperforms SSMF/PSCF; (d) share of routes vs. max. channel capacity; (e) max. route capacity vs. length.

Fig. 2(c) presents the percentage of cases (from a total of 945 combinations of attenuation and splice loss) where NANF outperforms SSMF/PSCF. Comparing NANF with IMI = -60 dB/km against SSMF, the share where the former has superior performance increases from 41% (27 dBm max. output power) to 58%, 73%, and 84% for a max. output power of 30, 33, and 36 dBm, respectively. If IMI = -45 dB/km, the superiority share varies from 28% (27 dBm) to 74% (36 dBm). If PSCF is the reference, NANF with an IMI value of -60 / -45 dB/km is superior to the former fiber type in between 23% / 7% (27 dBm) and 69% / 39% (36 dBm) of the cases.

The NANF performance in the DT network is also evaluated, assuming NANF with already demonstrated values of 0.18 dB, 0.21 dB/km, and -55 dB/km for the splice loss, fiber attenuation and IMI, respectively. Fig. 2(d) shows the fraction of routes per maximum channel capacity. When the maximum launch power is limited to 27 dBm, NANF outperforms SSMF, as a higher percentage of routes can use channels with higher capacity formats (e.g., 600, 700, and 800 Gbps). Still, PSCF is shown to slightly outperform NANF in this case. However, when assuming the use of higher output power amplifiers, NANF clearly outperforms PSCF, with around 60% of the routes supporting 800 Gbps, compared with 30%, 20%, and 10% when using PSCF, NANF (27 dBm) and SSMF, respectively. Finally, Fig. 2(e) presents the total route capacity (76 channels times the route data rate in Fig. 2(d)) versus the route length. The maximum route capacity of ≈ 60 Tbps is obtained for routes up to 240 km of SSMF, increasing to 320, 480, and 720 km when deploying NANF (27 dBm), PSCF, and NANF (36 dBm), respectively. For the longest route (1080 km), SSMF allows to transmit ≈ 30 Tbps, whereas PSCF and NANF (36 dBm) can support around 38 and 45 Tbps, respectively. Hence, for this length NANF (36 dBm) enables a capacity increase of 50% and 18%, when compared to SSMF and PSCF, respectively.

In conclusion, this paper presented a framework to evaluate the fiber and amplifier properties that can lead to NANF matching or surpassing SSMF and PSCF for high-capacity regio/long-haul network deployments. Particularly, assuming the availability of optical amplifiers with 36 dBm output power and that NANFs can be manufactured with an IMI equal or smaller than -55 dB/km, these fibers can feature an attenuation of 0.25 dB/km and splice losses of 0.22 dB and still deliver higher capacity in these networks than current best-in-class PSCF.

Acknowledgements

This work has received funding from EU Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under GA 101092766 (ALLEGRO), FCT/MECI through national funds and when applicable co-funded EU funds under UID/50008: Instituto de Telecomunicações.

References

- [1] H. Sakr *et al.*, Nat. Commun. **11**, 6030 (2020).
- [2] G. T. Jasion *et al.*, in *OFC*, (2022), p. Th4C.7.
- [3] Y. Chen *et al.*, in *OFC*, (2024), p. Th4A.8.
- [4] E. N. Fokoua *et al.*, Adv. Opt. Photonics **15**, 1 (2023).
- [5] A. Nespola *et al.*, JLT **39**, 813–820 (2021).
- [6] P. Poggiolini and F. Poletti, JLT **40**, 1605–1616 (2022).
- [7] https://mpbcommunications.com/en/site/products/network_ready_telecom_solutions/2RU-Series/boosters/index.html. Accessed: 2024-10-21.
- [8] G. S. Sticca *et al.*, in *OFC*, (2024), p. Tu3B.2.
- [9] D. Suslov *et al.*, Sci. Reports **11**, 8799 (2021).
- [10] A. Zhong *et al.*, JLT **42**, 2124–2130 (2024).
- [11] M. A. Iqbal *et al.*, in *CLEO*, (2022), p. SM2J.1.
- [12] A. Ferrari *et al.*, JOCN **12**, C31 (2020).
- [13] J. Pedro *et al.*, JOCN **14**, A154–A165 (2022).